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**“GLOBAL RAQAMLI INTEGRATSIYALASHUV:
2030-YILGACHA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHDA
TEXNOLOGIK VA INDUSTRIAL SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH
ORQALI MIKRO VA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQAROR
O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH DOLZARBLIGI”**

**“GLOBAL DIGITAL INTEGRATION: THE RELEVANCE OF
ENSURING MICRO AND MACROECONOMIC SUSTAINABLE
GROWTH THROUGH TECHNOLOGICAL AND INDUSTRIAL
DEVELOPMENT IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN
ECONOMY BY 2030”**

**«ГЛОБАЛЬНАЯ ЦИФРОВАЯ ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ:
АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО
МИКРО- И МАКРОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА ЧЕРЕЗ
РАЗВИТИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ И ИНДУСТРИАЛЬНОЙ
ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ В ПЕРЕХОДЕ К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ
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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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INSTITUTIONAL FEATURES OF STATE REGULATION OF PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. This thesis examines the institutional features of state regulation of product quality management in Uzbekistan. It analyzes the role of state bodies, authorized agencies, technical regulation institutions, conformity assessment bodies, testing laboratories, research institutions, business associations, and consumer organizations in ensuring product quality. The study highlights the importance of strengthening institutional coordination, developing regional quality control laboratories, improving human resource capacity, expanding technical and financial support mechanisms, and promoting a quality culture among consumers and producers.

Keywords: product quality, quality management, state regulation, institutional framework, technical regulation, conformity assessment, consumer protection, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezisdagi O'zbekistonda mahsulot sifatini boshqarishni davlat tomonidan tartibga solishning institutsional xususiyatlari tahlil qilingan. Unda davlat organlari, vakolatli idoralar, texnik tartibga solish institutlari, muvofiqlikni baholash organlari, sinov laboratoriyalari, ilmiy-tadqiqot muassasalari, tadbirkorlik birlashmalari va iste'molchilar tashkilotlarining mahsulot sifatini ta'minlashdagi o'rni yoritilgan. Tadqiqotda institutsional muvofiqlashtirishni kuchaytirish, hududiy sifat nazorati laboratoriyalarini rivojlantirish, kadrlar salohiyatini oshirish, texnik va moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini kengaytirish hamda iste'molchilar va ishlab chiqaruvchilar o'rtasida sifat madaniyatini shakllantirish muhimligi asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: mahsulot sifati, sifatni boshqarish, davlat tomonidan tartibga solish, institutsional asoslar, texnik tartibga solish, muvofiqlikni baholash, iste'molchilar huquqlarini himoya qilish, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация. В данном тезисе рассматриваются институциональные особенности государственного регулирования управления качеством продукции в Узбекистане. Проанализирована роль государственных органов, уполномоченных ведомств, институтов технического регулирования, органов оценки соответствия, испытательных лабораторий, научно-исследовательских учреждений, предпринимательских объединений и организаций потребителей в обеспечении качества продукции. В работе обоснована важность укрепления институциональной координации, развития региональных лабораторий контроля качества, повышения кадрового потенциала, расширения механизмов технической и финансовой поддержки, а также формирования культуры качества среди потребителей и производителей.

Ключевые слова: качество продукции, управление качеством, государственное регулирование, институциональные основы, техническое регулирование, оценка соответствия, защита прав потребителей, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

The institutional framework for state regulation of product quality management practices in the country is reflected in the activities of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Uzbekistan Agency for Technical Regulation, authorized state governing bodies in the field of technical regulation, state and economic management bodies involved in technical regulation activities, the national standardization body, the accreditation body, expert commissions in the field of technical regulation, conformity assessment bodies, and testing laboratories.

At the same time, the state regulation of product quality management practices in the country also involves specialized research institutions in the field of quality and standardization, including higher education institutions, business entities and their sectoral associations, such as the Food Industry Association, the Light Industry and Textile Association, and the Farmers' Association, as well as consumer associations. These stakeholders perform the following functions.

Specialized research institutes in the field of quality and standardization, including higher education institutions, develop scientifically grounded proposals and recommendations on product quality management, the improvement of national product standardization systems, integration with international quality standards, the enhancement of methodological foundations for quality assessment, and other related areas.

Business entities and consumer associations serve as an institutional form of public participation and oversight in ensuring the quality of manufactured products.

In the state regulation of product quality management practices, state control is carried out to support the circulation of safe, certified, and high-quality products in local consumer markets. These activities are implemented through the relevant state bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Justice, the Sanitary-Epidemiological Welfare and Public Health Service, the Agency for the Development of Competition and Consumer Protection, the Tax Committee, and the Committee for Veterinary and Livestock Development. Each of these institutions performs the relevant functional duties specified in Table 1.

Table 1. Institutional Foundations and Functions of State Regulation of Product Quality Control in Domestic Markets¹

№	Institution	Control Functions
1	Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan	Sale of substandard or counterfeit medicines and medical devices; Sale of falsified, uncertified, and non-registered medicines and medical products; Sale of prescription medicines without a prescription.
2	Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan	Production or distribution of products using another manufacturer's name or trademark (or similar marks), or the name of the place of origin; Violation of copyright and related rights; Infringement of rights to inventions, utility models, and industrial designs
3	Committee for Sanitary-Epidemiological Welfare and Public Health	Presence of insects and rodents in places of production, preparation, storage, and sale of food products; Preparation, storage, and sale of food products in unauthorized places; Sale of low-quality or spoiled food products; Unsatisfactory sanitary conditions in food preparation and sales areas.
4	Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan	Sale of alcohol and tobacco products with counterfeit excise stamps or without excise stamps; Sale of alcohol and tobacco products without mandatory digital marking codes; Sale of alcohol and tobacco products without authorization; Sale of low-quality alcohol and spirits
5	Competition Development and Consumer Rights Protection Committee	Absence of price labels on goods in retail outlets; Discrepancy between displayed prices and cashier receipt prices; Sale of expired goods; sale of medicines and medical devices with excessive mark-ups above regulated prices; Sale of goods without indication of production date and expiration date where required.
6	Committee for Veterinary and Livestock Development	Production or sale of unfit meat and dairy products; Sale of meat and dairy products without veterinary inspection; Sale of meat and dairy products in unauthorized places; Transportation of meat products in unauthorized vehicles.

This system contributes to the protection of consumer rights, the strengthening of product safety and certification mechanisms, the prevention of risks associated with products that do not meet established requirements, and the provision of high-quality consumer goods to the population.

According to the conducted analysis, several areas requiring further improvement have been identified in the state regulation of product quality management in the country. These areas are reflected in the normative-legal, institutional, cultural, and practical dimensions of promoting and implementing quality management principles. Strengthening these aspects can contribute to the further improvement of product quality management mechanisms, enhance the effectiveness of consumer protection measures, and support the broader development of quality-oriented practices.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In our view, based on the current priorities in the field of state regulation of product quality management practices, it is appropriate to implement the following measures in the coming years.

First, institutional reforms should be further deepened by establishing coordination councils among authorized bodies involved in the state regulation of product quality management practices. In addition, regional quality control laboratories and centers should be established across different territories.

Second, human resource capacity should be improved through the development of educational programs in higher education institutions aimed at training specialists in quality management and enhancing their professional qualifications.

¹ President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Resolution No. PQ-110 "On Additional Measures Aimed at Ensuring the Population with High-Quality Consumer Goods," dated April 4, 2023.

Third, technical and financial support mechanisms should be expanded. This includes establishing a system of subsidies and grants for manufacturing enterprises that have implemented or are in the process of implementing international quality standards, as well as introducing digitalized product quality control systems in domestic markets.

Fourth, a quality culture should be promoted among the population and business entities. This can be achieved by implementing public awareness measures on consumer rights and forming a unified and consistent understanding of product quality between consumers and producers.

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